

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Reliability of SiC power devices to thermal neutrons: analysis of ¹⁰B-impurities effect</i>
Project TA identifier	TA05-126
General application	Ground level
Type of test	SEEs
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Date(s) of the experiment	27-28 November 2023
Facility	ILL - Tennis
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	24 h

Objectives of the experiments

Silicon carbide (SiC) is a wide bandgap semiconductor with promising properties for use in harsh environments, such as in outer space or in high-energy accelerators [1-2]. Due to the superiority of 4H-SiC devices in terms of physical properties and high displacement threshold energy, these devices have been studied under different radiation environments such as with heavy-ions, protons and terrestrial neutrons [1,3,4,5]. However, little information is available concerning the reliability of SiC power devices with thermal neutrons [6]. Despite the low energy, thermal neutrons could represent a reliability issue for SiC power devices. In fact, it is well known that metallic impurities such as Boron (B) are commonly incorporated in the boule crystals during the growth process, with densities that can vary depending on the manufacturer [7]. ¹⁰B, which is ~20% in nature, has a high cross-section for thermal neutron absorption (~3840 barns for 0.025 eV) leading to ¹⁰B(n,α)⁷Li reactions accompanied by 0.48 MeV gamma emission. The produced charged particles generate electron hole pairs in the semiconductor as they lose their energy in the depletion region. Such effects are highly unwanted and may lead to reliability issues or even complete destruction of the device.

Furthermore, the examination of material properties is of both fundamental and technological importance. Therefore, the analysis of thermal neutron induced modifications in the material properties are of interest as B is present in SiC devices. The induced reaction of a thermal neutron and B will give an insight into the response of the semiconductor to the induced helium and lithium production. Previous MCTS performed on devices exposed to heavy ions showed a change in the distribution of defects related to Boron [8].

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Experiment test report

Single event burnout (SEB) testing has been performed on commercial SiC power devices (MOSFETs and diodes) in order to assess the reliability with thermal neutrons. Commercial bare dies (n-type doped with nitrogen) were selected as devices under test (DUTs). As the amount of B impurities can vary among devices produced by different manufacturer, multiple devices were chosen from the market. The devices were connected in parallel to the high voltage, each of them with an individual current limiting resistor between the device and the SMU output, following the military standard regulations (MIL-STD-750E M1080.1). Similar setup and procedure as described in [5] was used. The devices were tested as bare dies, installed on a DCB board with three terminations, as in a TO-247 package.

The following references were selected as devices under test (DUTs):

Reference	Manufacturer	Type of device	R _{DS(ON)} [mOhm]	Max Voltage [kV]
C2M0080120D	Cree/Wolfspeed	Power MOSFET	80	1.2
CPW4-1200-S024	Cree/Wolfspeed	Power diode		1.2
Non-commercial	Infineon	Power MOSFET	12	1.2
Non-commercial	Infineon	Power diode		1.2

All the references were tested at 1100 V which was the maximum voltage of the Keithley SMU 2410 used for the setup. No SEB were observed during irradiation. 8 DUTs were tested for each reference at minimum fluences of $5 \times 10^{10} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Additional electrical measurements including time-dependent-dielectric breakdown (TDDB) will be performed, to assess the reliability of the gate oxide of the tested SiC power MOSFETs. However, since the sample have just been released due to their activity, the additional measurements have not been performed yet.

Furthermore, the analysis of thermal neutron induced modifications in the material properties are of fundamental and technological importance. Therefore, SiC wafers from the manufacturer Cree/Wolfspeed, with epitaxial thickness of 10 μm and doping of $4 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (same as used for commercial devices) were also irradiated at different fluences $> 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The post-irradiation study will involve a profound analysis of the created defects and their distribution, which shall be conducted with deep-level-transient spectroscopy (DLTS) and minority-carrier-transient spectroscopy (MCTS). Similar analysis will also be performed on the irradiated diodes.

In conclusion, no SEB were observed when exposing commercial SiC power MOSFETs and diodes as bare dies to thermal neutrons. However, additional electrical measurements, MCTS and DLTS are needed to further study the presence of latent damage and other sign of material degradation.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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